

Article

Defining XR-Specific Teacher Competencies: Extending the DigCompEdu Framework for Immersive Education

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Abstract: Extended Reality (XR) technologies—including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR)—offer transformative opportunities for education by enabling immersive and interactive learning experiences. In this study, we employed a mixed-methods approach that combined systematic desk research with an expert member check to evaluate existing pedagogical frameworks for XR integration. We analyzed several established models (e.g., TPACK, TIM, SAMR, CAMIL, and DigCompEdu) to assess their strengths and limitations in addressing the unique competencies required for XR-supported teaching. Our results indicate that, while these models offer valuable insights into technology integration, they often fall short in specifying XR-specific competencies. Consequently, we extended the DigCompEdu framework by identifying and refining concrete building blocks for teacher professionalization in XR. The conclusions drawn from this research underscore the necessity for targeted professional development that equips educators with the practical skills needed to effectively implement XR in diverse educational settings, thereby providing actionable strategies for fostering digital innovation in teaching and learning.

Keywords: augmented reality; digital competencies; educational frameworks; extended reality; professional development; teacher professionalization; virtual reality

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1. Introduction

Teaching and learning can often be supported by the use of technology. The integration of digital applications, such as virtual reality (VR), is increasingly prominent in educational contexts. VR can be implemented in various ways and is applicable in primary education, secondary education, and vocational education. In vocational and higher education, VR has been implemented to facilitate the acquisition of practical skills, among other applications. In addition to the use of VR in education, Extended Reality (XR) combines augmented reality (AR), virtual reality, and mixed reality (MR). XR technology facilitates capabilities that were previously unattainable or less viable with conventional technologies; for instance, its spatial dimension permits dynamic navigation within virtual environments, thereby enhancing the representation of physical experiences. For instance, a history instructor may utilize VR to immerse students in a virtual reconstruction of an ancient city, while an AR application in a biology class could overlay detailed anatomical information onto a human body model, thereby making abstract concepts more tangible.

However, it is not automatic that technology enriches education; the impact of these developments, such as XR, depends on the educational design and how educators implement the technology [1]. A challenge of implementing technology in education is that it makes

the educational process more complex. Teaching is already a complex process influenced by various factors that cannot all be integrated into technology. Most adaptive learning materials necessitate the presence of an instructor to support students encountering difficulties or conceptual impasses. Kavanagh et al. [2] show, in their systematic review, that widespread adoption is still pending due to various limitations in technology, costs, and logistics. In addition to teaching and integrating technology into teaching being a complex process, there has also been limited theoretical foundation regarding the design and development of XR applications based on learning theories and research on pedagogical use and effects on learning outcomes, cognitively and affectively [3,4].

Finally, it is important to emphasize that there is still insufficient knowledge about the use of XR in education because the technology is still developing. Not all applications and limitations of these technologies are known [5]. Additionally, De Lange and Lodewijk [5] and others conclude that the novelty effect of VR being a new technological development makes it challenging at this stage of implementation to make definitive statements about the effect of VR on students' learning performance. The novelty effect refers to learners temporarily exerting a higher level of effort and attention due to using technology that is new to them [6]. Although this initial boost can enhance engagement, research indicates that an overemphasis on the immersive features of XR may lead to cognitive overload or distraction if not aligned with clear educational objectives [7]. Thus, it is essential for educators to possess the skills necessary to balance the engaging qualities of XR with the structured delivery of content, ensuring that the technology serves to enhance, rather than detract from, the learning process.

International research into XR in education reveals significant transformative potential when these technologies are embedded in well-designed instructional strategies. Early foundational work by Slater and Wilbur [8] and Milgram and Kishino [9] laid the groundwork for understanding the phenomena of "presence" and user–environment interaction in virtual spaces. More recent studies (e.g., [10,11]) have further illustrated that XR can enhance engagement, support personalized learning, and facilitate the simulation of complex scenarios. Nonetheless, the literature also emphasizes that the teacher's role is crucial: without the appropriate pedagogical and technical skills, the advantages of XR cannot be fully realized.

Given this context, it is imperative to investigate the specific competencies educators require for effective XR integration. Enhanced teacher competencies in this domain can lead to concrete improvements in teaching and learning. For instance, educators skilled in XR applications can design interactive simulations that allow students to manipulate 3D models in real time or conduct virtual field trips that provide immersive context-rich learning experiences. Such concrete examples highlight how the development of targeted XR-related competencies not only boosts student engagement and motivation, but also contributes directly to improved learning outcomes.

In light of these developments, the present article aims to deepen our understanding of the potential of XR technologies in education by examining existing pedagogical models and frameworks—such as TPACK and DigCompEdu—and identifying the specific competencies educators require for effective XR integration. This study seeks to formulate concrete building blocks for teacher professionalization in the context of XR, thereby contributing to a more evidence-based approach to the adoption of immersive technologies in diverse educational settings.

1.1. Defining XR, VR, AR, and MR

Extended Reality (XR) is an overarching term that encompasses a spectrum of technologies that blur the boundaries between the physical and digital worlds. Within this umbrella, three principal forms can be distinguished:

- Virtual reality (VR): A technology that creates a completely digital environment in which users are fully immersed, effectively replacing their physical surroundings with a simulated reality. This immersion is typically achieved through head-mounted displays and various sensory input devices [12].
- Augmented reality (AR): A technology that overlays digital information or images onto the real world, allowing users to experience both the physical and digital simultaneously. AR applications are commonly accessed via smartphones, tablets, or specialized eyewear [13].
- Mixed reality (MR): A hybrid form in which digital and physical objects are not only displayed side by side but can also interact with one another in real time. This interactivity creates novel opportunities for dynamic learning experiences that combine aspects of both VR and AR [9].

1.2. Aim of This Research

For these reasons, the current article focuses on gaining a better understanding of the benefits of Extended Reality (XR) technologies in education, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR). We explore the application of XR using pedagogical models. There are many models available focusing on the implementation of ICT in education in general. We will discuss models from the teaching perspective, rather than models solely formulated from the student's perspective and digital literacy. By contextualizing XR technologies within models and frameworks, we aim to outline practical strategies for educators to effectively integrate XR into their teaching practices. We also focus on the competencies that educators need in order to integrate XR into their teaching practices.

Based on the aims, the research questions have been determined as follows:

- How do existing models and frameworks for digitalization in education, such as the TPACK model, align with the needs and challenges of teaching with XR in educational settings?
- What are concrete building blocks on competencies for educators from the perspective of XR?

2. Research Method

To fulfil the set aim of this research and answer the research questions determined above, the desk research method was used [14], followed by an expert member check [15]. This mixed-methods approach aligns with qualitative research designs that emphasize in-depth understanding of complex phenomena (e.g., [16]). The research questions are addressed following a tiered approach, beginning with a broad exploration of existing frameworks and subsequently narrowing down to the specific competencies required by educators. Due to this tiered approach of the research questions, the first research question was investigated by following a desk research approach; via the search engine Google Scholar, existing frameworks in this area were initially sought. After subsequently applying exclusion criteria, it was determined which frameworks were applicable to our research. For the remaining frameworks, it was determined what the advantages and disadvantages of these frameworks were within our context. This method is described in more detail later in this section.

The second research question was investigated by combining desk research with an expert member check. The expert member check serves as a critical validation step, enhancing the credibility and reliability of our findings by incorporating feedback from practitioners actively engaged in XR-supported education [17]. This second research question focuses on what specific competencies teachers need to be able to teach with XR. Prior to this research, it was already known that it might become difficult to use existing frameworks to clarify the palette of competencies teachers need to teach with XR. This is because most frameworks do not specifically address these competencies. Therefore, it was decided to build on the framework that most concretely addresses teacher competencies (in the case of a lack of choice between multiple frameworks).

Because teacher professionalization in the field of XR has, until recently, been an underexposed topic [18], we decided to address the answer to the second research question in a form that can be excellently used for teacher professionalization activities, specifically, a card set. Each card in this set provides a nuanced elaboration of certain competencies needed for XR-supported education and a series of learning activities related to that competency, outlining the palette of possibilities for providing education with XR from that competency. In education in the Netherlands, for example, such card sets are often used, but a card is referred to as a 'building block'. Engaging workshop participants with these sets of building blocks encourages critical reflection on the applicability of each component to their professional context, as illustrated by a card set on 'teacher professionalization in ICT'. An example of a set of building blocks that has also been translated into English is that of the award-winning *Lessons for learning*: <https://3starlearningexperiences.wordpress.com/2020/04/28/12-building-blocks-to-use-learning-technologies-effectively-all-in-one> (accessed on 24 January 2025).

As stated above, the second research question is answered from a combination of desk research [14] and an expert member check [15]. After an initial phase of desk research, we performed the expert member check during a live meeting of the Erasmus project Pedagogical Alliance for XR-Technology in (Teacher) Education (PAX). Members of the PAX consortium are exceptionally well suited to assess what has initially been conceived, as they have an excellent view of what XR-supported learning activities look like in practice. The consortium members were asked to act as experts during a member check, which aimed to determine the extent to which adjustments were needed from the originally conceived collection of XR-related building blocks, based on what those experts had already experienced in practice. The findings from the expert member check were subsequently employed to refine the set of building blocks, thereby producing a framework that more accurately reflects the practical implementation of XR in educational settings.

2.1. Specification of Method for Answering Research Question 1: "How Do Existing Models and Frameworks for Digitalization in Education, Such as the TPACK Model, Align with the Needs and Challenges of Teaching with XR in Educational Settings?"

- (1) Relevant frameworks are sought by searching via Google Scholar. Recent advancements in academic search tools have led to a growing acceptance of Google Scholar as a robust instrument for searching the literature, while—compared to traditional databases—it offers a broader coverage that includes grey literature, conference proceedings, and other non-conventional sources, an advantage particularly pertinent to rapidly evolving fields like XR [19]. The following search string is used for searching the literature: [[virtual reality OR VR OR augmented reality OR AR OR extended reality OR XR] AND [higher education OR K-12 education OR primary education OR vocational education] AND [effectiveness OR knowledge OR skill OR attitude OR teacher training OR teacher educators OR pre-service teachers] AND framework].

- (2) Then, exclusion criteria are applied to the results from Google Scholar until saturation occurs. A results page from Google Scholar has 10 references to sources. 'Saturation' in this context means that the examination of result pages continues until a complete page no longer leads to the discovery of an additional relevant model. The applied exclusion criteria are as follows:
 - (a) The article turns out not to be about a framework.
 - (b) The framework the article discusses is not fundamental in nature, but is a variation on a framework that has already been published. This criterion is not applied because the variations on those frameworks would not be relevant, but because there are so many variations on frameworks that the found collection of frameworks would become so large that it would no longer fit within the scope of this article.
 - (c) The framework the article writes about does not concern teaching and learning, but something else (e.g., technology acceptance).
- (3) The resulting collection of articles is first used to generally describe the found frameworks to give the reader an impression of these frameworks. Questions that are clarified include the following: What is the origin of the framework? How is the framework structured? What can the framework be used for? Then, it goes into more detail on both the advantages and disadvantages of the framework. Questions that come up include the following: Which questions can this framework answer well? What can this framework make insightful? To what extent is it a usable framework for teachers? What are the shortcomings of the framework? What does the framework not take into account? Where does the framework miss the mark?

2.2. Specification of Method for Answering Research Question 2: "What Are Concrete Building Blocks on Competencies for Educators from the Perspective of XR?"

- (1) Based on the collection of frameworks discussed in the first research question, it is gauged to what extent those frameworks specifically address teacher competencies. The second research question builds on the framework that does this most concretely.
- (2) For each competency, it is determined to what extent XR-based activities are already mentioned with the possible learning activities linked to them.
- (3) Based on what comes forward in that determination, two ways of responding are possible:
 - (a) As soon as it involves a learning activity that can be linked to both XR and other technologies, that learning activity is reformulated into an XR-based learning activity.
 - (b) In the case that certain XR-based learning activities are not yet mentioned with that competency, those XR-learning activities are added to that competency's description.
- (4) Subsequently, a reflective description is provided of what can be said about groups of competencies regarding how learning activities with XR can be supported and what that then means for what the teacher needs to be capable of.
- (5) Building on this, we describe what the necessity of teaching with XR during those activities then means for how teachers need to be professionalized concerning that collection of competencies. This step also concludes the desk research phase. The following steps aim to better align the created building blocks for XR-related teacher competencies with practice.
- (6) The next step then focuses on an expert member check to align the building blocks with practice. Before approaching the experts for this, the building blocks prepared so far are processed into a form specifically designed for use in professionalization

workshops. Concretely, this means that each teacher competency with related XR-based learning activities is printed on a separate card. Together, these cards form a card set, which each participant can use physically during the expert member check meeting.

- (7) The meeting with experts starts with an introduction about the how and why of better aligning the collection of XR-based teacher competencies with practice and how the attendees can fulfil an expert role by performing the member check. The continuation of the meeting consists of three phases:
 - (a) First, the attending experts individually delve into their card set with XR-based teacher competencies. They individually determine the extent to which they assess the described teacher competencies and learning activities to be in line with practice, and note for themselves everything they find that should be changed or is missing.
 - (b) Subsequently, the experts discuss in pairs and exchange with each other which changes they deem necessary.
 - (c) Finally, findings and thoughts are exchanged in the complete group. Discussions were systematically documented for subsequent analysis.
- (8) The findings of the expert meeting are processed in the card set so that it better aligns with the practice of the experts. After completing this, the card set serves a dual purpose:
 - (a) The card set answers the second research question in a nuanced, concrete, and practice-aligned way.
 - (b) The card set can then be directly used to support teacher professionalization activities aimed at the development of XR-related teacher competencies.

3. Results

3.1. Results Relating to Research Question 1: Exploring the Application of XR in Education Through Various Pedagogical Models

XR presents transformative opportunities for enhancing teaching and learning through immersive and interactive technologies such as VR, AR, and MR. To systematically explore XR's potential in educational settings, it is beneficial to consider established pedagogical frameworks. This section examines the application of XR in education using different models and frameworks. The analysis begins with a description of the various pedagogical models, followed by a detailed discussion of the respective advantages and disadvantages associated with the integration of XR in educational settings.

3.1.1. TPACK Model: Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge

The *Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge* (TPACK) framework is a widely recognized construct designed to facilitate the integration of technology into education. Originally developed by Mishra and Koehler [20], it builds upon Shulman's [21] concept of *Pedagogical Content Knowledge* (PCK), which focuses on the blending of subject matter expertise with instructional methods. In Shulman's framework, PCK refers to the best ways to organize, adapt, and present content for effective teaching. Mishra and Koehler extended this model to include *Technological Knowledge* (TK) in response to the increasing prominence of computers and educational software in classrooms. As such, TPACK highlights the complex interaction between three core domains of teacher knowledge: *Content Knowledge* (CK), *Pedagogical Knowledge* (PK), and *Technological Knowledge* (TK).

Content Knowledge pertains to a teacher's expertise in the subject matter they are teaching. *Pedagogical Knowledge* involves an understanding of various teaching methods and strategies for facilitating student learning. *Technological Knowledge*, in contrast, includes the

ability to utilize digital tools and resources, such as software and hardware, to enhance the educational experience. These three areas converge at multiple points, forming *Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)*, *Technological Pedagogical Knowledge (TPK)*, and *Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)*. At the heart of this intersection lies *Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)*, which represents a comprehensive understanding of how technology can be integrated into teaching to support both pedagogy and content effectively (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mishra and Koehler's [20] TPACK model.

This integrated model is often visualized as a Venn diagram, where the overlapping areas emphasize how content, pedagogy, and technology are interrelated, and how teachers must navigate these intersections to deliver high-quality instruction. For instance, in a STEM classroom, educators may employ XR technologies such as VR to investigate complex biological concepts (e.g., the structure of DNA), thereby rendering abstract content more accessible and engaging for students. Consequently, the TPACK framework offers a structured approach for integrating innovative technologies that enhance the dynamism and interactivity of teaching practices. The TPACK model is seen as a promising approach for incorporating XR technologies in technical and STEM education, providing a foundation for educators to use these tools in a didactically effective manner [22]. However, despite its widespread use, the TPACK framework is not without criticism. Below, both the advantages and disadvantages of the framework are outlined.

One of the main strengths of the TPACK framework is its emphasis on the importance of integrating technology, pedagogy, and Content Knowledge in education. Teaching is inherently a complex and multifaceted activity, and the model encourages educators to adopt a holistic understanding of how these knowledge areas interact. By highlighting this integrated approach, the framework offers a more nuanced view of technology integration, which is essential for developing effective teaching practices.

Moreover, the TPACK framework serves as a reflective tool for educators, helping them to evaluate and ensure that all relevant aspects—content, pedagogy, and technology—are adequately considered when integrating ICT into their teaching. This reflective aspect makes TPACK valuable for designing instructional strategies that incorporate technology meaningfully, ensuring that it enhances rather than detracts from the learning experience.

Despite these strengths, some researchers have raised concerns regarding the practical applicability of the TPACK framework. According to Brantley-Dias and Ertmer [23], some of the framework's concepts may be too specific for meaningful application, while others are overly expansive and, thus, difficult to operationalize. The existence of seven distinct knowledge types within the model can create confusion and make it challenging for educators to differentiate clearly between overlapping areas (e.g., distinguishing between Technological Knowledge (TK) and Technological Content Knowledge (TCK)).

Another limitation of the framework is that it does not account for important contextual factors that influence the successful implementation of ICT in education, such as teacher beliefs, school culture, or the broader institutional vision for technology integration. These factors can significantly affect how teachers adopt and use technology in their classrooms, yet they are not explicitly addressed within the TPACK model, which may lead to gaps when applying the framework in real-world educational settings.

The TPACK framework offers a robust conceptualization of how technology can be integrated into teaching practices by acknowledging the complex relationships between content, pedagogy, and technology. Its utility as both a reflective tool and a guide for educators to incorporate technology into their classrooms is well recognized, especially in contexts like STEM education and the use of advanced technologies like XR. However, its complexity and lack of consideration for external factors such as institutional support or teacher beliefs may limit its practical application in some educational environments. As such, while TPACK provides a strong theoretical foundation, its implementation requires careful adaptation to specific teaching contexts.

3.1.2. The Technology Integration Matrix

The *Technology Integration Matrix* (TIM) is a framework developed by the University of South Florida in collaboration with the Florida Department of Education [24]. The original purpose of this framework was to assess and support technology integration in educational environments, particularly focusing on how effectively technology is integrated into teaching and learning processes. The TIM is structured as a matrix that combines five levels of technology integration—*entry*, *adoption*, *adaptation*, *infusion*, and *transformation*—with five characteristics of meaningful learning environments: *active*, *collaborative*, *constructive*, *authentic*, and *goal-directed* (see Figure 2). This dual-axis structure allows educators to map the integration of technology in their classrooms and measure progress toward the more sophisticated and impactful use of technological tools in education.

The primary application of the TIM is to provide a comprehensive guide for teachers and administrators to assess the degree to which technology is incorporated into instructional practices. It serves as both a diagnostic tool and a developmental guide, assisting educators in identifying their current level of technology integration and offering pathways for improvement. By using the TIM, schools and districts can promote more effective teaching strategies that leverage technology to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

The Technology Integration Matrix Table of Summary Descriptors

The Technology Integration Matrix (TIM) provides a framework for describing and targeting the use of technology to enhance learning. The TIM incorporates five interdependent characteristics of meaningful learning environments: active, collaborative, constructive, authentic, and goal-directed. These characteristics are associated with five levels of technology integration: entry, adoption, adaptation, infusion, and transformation. Together, the five characteristics of meaningful learning environments and five levels of technology integration create a matrix of 25 cells, as illustrated below.

	LEVELS OF TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION					
	ENTRY LEVEL	ADOPTION LEVEL	ADAPTATION LEVEL	INFUSION LEVEL	TRANSFORMATION LEVEL	
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LEARNING ENVIRONMENT	ACTIVE LEARNING Students are actively engaged in using technology as a tool rather than passively receiving information from the technology.	Active Entry Information passively received	Active Adoption Conventional, procedural use of tools	Active Adaptation Conventional independent use of tools; some student choice and exploration	Active Infusion Choice of tools and regular, self-directed use	Active Transformation Extensive and unconventional use of tools
	COLLABORATIVE LEARNING Students use technology tools to collaborate with others rather than working individually at all times.	Collaborative Entry Individual student use of technology tools	Collaborative Adoption Collaborative use of tools in conventional ways	Collaborative Adaptation Collaborative use of tools; some student choice and exploration	Collaborative Infusion Choice of tools and regular use for collaboration	Collaborative Transformation Collaboration with peers, outside experts, and others in ways that may not be possible without technology
	CONSTRUCTIVE LEARNING Students use technology tools to connect new information to their prior knowledge rather than to passively receive information.	Constructive Entry Information delivered to students	Constructive Adoption Guided, conventional use for building knowledge	Constructive Adaptation Independent use for building knowledge; some student choice and exploration	Constructive Infusion Choice and regular use for building knowledge	Constructive Transformation Extensive and unconventional use of technology tools to build knowledge
	AUTHENTIC LEARNING Students use technology tools to link learning activities to the world beyond the instructional setting rather than working on decontextualized assignments.	Authentic Entry Technology use unrelated to the world outside of the instructional setting	Authentic Adoption Guided use in activities with some meaningful context	Authentic Adaptation Independent use in activities connected to students' lives; some student choice and exploration	Authentic Infusion Choice of tools and regular use in meaningful activities	Authentic Transformation Innovative use for higher-order learning activities connected to the world beyond the instructional setting
	GOAL-DIRECTED LEARNING Students use technology tools to set goals, plan activities, monitor progress, and evaluate results rather than simply completing assignments without reflection.	Goal-Directed Entry Directions given; step-by-step task monitoring	Goal-Directed Adoption Conventional and procedural use of tools to plan or monitor	Goal-Directed Adaptation Purposeful use of tools to plan and monitor; some student choice and exploration	Goal-Directed Infusion Flexible and seamless use of tools to plan and monitor	Goal-Directed Transformation Extensive and higher-order use of tools to plan and monitor

Figure 2. The Technology Integration Matrix, developed by the University of South Florida and the Florida Department of Education [24].

One of the advantages of the TIM is its adaptability across different educational contexts. The framework's clear structure and multimedia examples help teachers understand how to apply technology meaningfully. It encourages a shift from teacher-centered to student-centered learning environments. Nonetheless, a significant limitation of the framework is that it presupposes educators' familiarity with the matrix and its hierarchical levels, thereby necessitating additional training and resources that may not be available in all educational settings. Furthermore, while the TIM emphasizes technology use, it may

not adequately address the broader pedagogical or systemic factors that impact student engagement, such as socio-economic challenges or access to resources.

The TIM excels at answering questions related to how well technology is integrated into the teaching process and how this integration supports specific learning outcomes. It can provide insights into the level of engagement and collaboration fostered by the use of technology in the classroom. However, the framework does not fully account for other influences on student engagement, such as personal motivation or external distractions, and it may overlook deeper instructional issues unrelated to technology. Consequently, it may miss the mark when evaluating engagement in environments where technology is present but not central to the teaching strategy.

While the TIM is useful for teachers looking to enhance technology integration, it is less applicable for educators in low-tech environments or those who prioritize other instructional methods. As such, the framework is more suitable for schools with a commitment to advancing digital learning.

3.1.3. SAMR Model: Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, Redefinition

The Substitution Augmentation Modification Redefinition (SAMR) model (see Figure 3) was introduced by Ruben Puentedura to help educators integrate technology into their teaching practices [25]. The model is structured as a four-level taxonomy, where each level—*substitution*, *augmentation*, *modification*, and *redefinition*—represents an increasing degree of technological integration and transformation of the learning process. *Substitution* involves simply replacing traditional tools with digital ones without changing the task, whereas *redefinition* refers to the creation of entirely new tasks that would be impossible without technology.

Figure 3. Puentedura's [25] SAMR model.

The SAMR model can be used by teachers to assess how they are utilizing technology in their classrooms and to guide them in enhancing their teaching methods through technological tools. It encourages progression from basic uses of technology toward more transformative practices. For example, moving from using a word processor to replace pen and paper (substitution) to creating interactive multimedia projects that engage students in novel ways (redefinition).

One of the key advantages of the SAMR model is its simplicity and ease of use. It provides educators with a clear structured pathway for integrating technology into their

teaching, and it emphasizes the potential of technology to enhance learning experiences. However, this same simplicity can be a drawback. The model's hierarchical nature suggests that higher levels of the framework are inherently better, which may not always be the case depending on the educational context. Furthermore, the model focuses primarily on the product of technology use rather than the pedagogical processes involved, limiting its applicability to more nuanced teaching strategies.

The SAMR model is particularly adept at answering questions about how technology can transform educational tasks and increase student engagement through digital tools. It provides insights into how specific technological interventions can reshape the nature of classroom activities, potentially leading to deeper learning outcomes. However, it falls short in addressing the broader contextual factors that influence technology integration, such as teacher beliefs, available resources, and student needs. The model does not account for the complexities of different educational settings, making it less useful in environments where resources or support for technology are limited.

The SAMR model offers a valuable framework for educators to assess and enhance their technological integration; however, its inherent simplicity may lead to an oversimplification of the multifaceted nature of teaching and learning processes. Its limited consideration of contextual factors and pedagogical processes necessitates that educators exercise caution when applying the model without integrating these critical elements. Moreover, the model overlooks the fact that sometimes a simple substitution of technology may be the most appropriate choice, depending on the learning objectives. Thus, while the SAMR model has value, it should be supplemented with other frameworks that take a more holistic approach to teaching with technology.

3.1.4. Cognitive Affective Model of Immersive Learning (CAMIL)

The *Cognitive Affective Model of Immersive Learning* (CAMIL) provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how immersive virtual reality (IVR) can influence learning processes. Developed by Guido Makransky and Gustav Petersen in 2021, the CAMIL [6] synthesizes existing research on IVR-based education to explain how various cognitive and affective factors interact to promote learning. The model arose in response to the increasing use of VR in educational contexts and the need for a theoretical model to guide its application. The CAMIL builds on research that suggests that instructional methods designed for less immersive media can be adapted to IVR, but it emphasizes that the unique affordances of immersive technologies, particularly presence and agency, interact with instructional methods in ways that influence learning outcomes.

The CAMIL is structured around three primary technological affordances: *immersion*, *interactivity*, and *representational fidelity*, all of which contribute to the user's sense of presence and agency. Immersion refers to the degree to which the VR system creates a lifelike detailed environment that isolates the user from the physical world and immerses them in a virtual one [26]. The level of *immersion* is determined by factors such as resolution, frame rate, and the quality of visual representation [27]. *Interactivity*, also known as control factors, relates to the user's ability to manipulate the environment. This sense of control is key to the user's experience of agency, or the feeling that they can generate and control actions within the virtual space [28]. Finally, *representational fidelity* refers to how realistically the environment is rendered and how smoothly transitions and changes within the environment are represented [29]. These three elements are interrelated, with immersion and interactivity significantly enhancing the user's sense of presence and agency.

Presence is central to the CAMIL and is defined as the psychological state of "being there" in the virtual environment, even though the user is physically located elsewhere. It is closely linked to immersion, as the more immersive the environment, the stronger the

user's sense of presence. Agency is similarly influenced by the degree of interactivity in the system, where higher levels of control over the environment lead to a stronger feeling of agency. Together, presence and agency shape the user's engagement with the virtual environment and are crucial for fostering effective learning experiences in IVR.

The CAMIL framework (see Figure 4) identifies six key cognitive and affective factors—*interest, intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, embodiment, cognitive load, and self-regulation*—that are influenced by presence and agency and contribute to learning outcomes. These factors impact how learners acquire *factual, conceptual, and procedural* knowledge, and how they *transfer* this knowledge to new contexts. The CAMIL has practical implications for instructional design in IVR as it highlights the need to tailor instructional methods to enhance presence and agency, thereby increasing motivation, engagement, and knowledge transfer.

Figure 4. Makransky and Petersen's [6] CAMIL framework.

One of the advantages of the CAMIL is its ability to explain the interaction between media and instructional methods. It offers a nuanced understanding of how VR can be used to improve learning outcomes by focusing on its unique affordances. However, it also has limitations. The CAMIL does not fully address individual differences in learners, such as spatial ability or susceptibility to cyber sickness, nor does it account for external factors like usability or social influence. Furthermore, the framework may be less applicable to less immersive technologies, as its focus is specifically on the affordances of high-immersion environments.

In conclusion, the CAMIL provides valuable insights into how immersive technologies can be effectively used in education by identifying the key features that influence learning. Its emphasis on the interaction between immersion, interactivity, and representational fidelity makes it a powerful tool for understanding and optimizing learning in virtual

environments. However, its usability for teachers depends on their ability to integrate these features into their instructional designs, which may require additional training and resources.

3.1.5. Triple E Model: Engagement, Enhancement, Extension

Kolb's Triple E framework [30] is designed to help educators critically evaluate the use of technology in their teaching practices, ensuring that it effectively contributes to student learning outcomes. The framework emphasizes three core components—*engagement*, *enhancement*, and *extension*—each of which addresses how technology integrates into the learning process by engaging students, enhancing their understanding, and extending their learning into real-world contexts. Primarily intended for K-12 education, the model is practical and adaptable, providing teachers with a clear and structured guide for aligning technology with pedagogical goals.

The Triple E framework builds on previous models, aiming to fill gaps left by these earlier approaches. For instance, the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) model provides a theoretical understanding of the interplay between content, pedagogy, and technology. However, it falls short in offering practical guidelines on how specific tool affordances can transform learning. Kolb's framework addresses this need by offering a more straightforward pragmatic approach that focuses on actual learning outcomes rather than just theoretical alignment.

Similarly, while the TIM (Technology Integration Matrix) model provides a detailed framework that evaluates technology integration across five levels and five characteristics of meaningful learning environments, it can be cumbersome and time-consuming for daily use. Although it offers a thorough structure, the TIM model struggles to directly measure the impact of technology on content-specific learning outcomes, an area where the Triple E framework offers more direct support.

The SAMR (*substitution, augmentation, modification, redefinition*) model simplifies the process of understanding technology integration by highlighting how tools can be used to enhance or transform traditional teaching methods. While SAMR effectively shows the levels of technological transformation, it prioritizes the tool over the learning outcomes, a limitation the Triple E framework seeks to address by focusing on how well technology supports the learning process rather than how innovatively it is used.

The Triple E framework (see Figure 5) is structured around three key components:

- *Engagement*: Active and social engagement in learning, where technology supports meaningful interaction with content.
- *Enhancement*: Technology adds value by improving the efficiency or effectiveness of learning, helping students understand concepts more deeply.
- *Extension*: Technology helps bridge learning within the classroom to real-world applications, fostering authentic learning experiences.

To apply the Triple E framework, educators must first identify the learning outcomes and then select the appropriate technology tools. They subsequently assess how well the chosen technology aligns with the three components of engagement, enhancement, and extension using guiding questions provided by the framework.

Advantages of the Triple E Framework

- **Practical focus**: The framework provides a clear and actionable evaluation guide for K-12 educators, making it especially useful in designing individual lessons.
- **Learning outcomes first**: The model emphasizes student learning as the primary focus, ensuring that technology serves as a tool to achieve educational goals rather than as an end in itself.

- Encourages social and active learning: It highlights the importance of interaction and collaboration in learning, encouraging educators to design lessons that engage students actively and socially.
- Instructional strategies: The framework incorporates instructional strategies and provides examples to help teachers integrate technology effectively in the classroom.
- Validated tool: The model is validated for designing lessons that incorporate technology meaningfully, contributing to a teacher's pedagogical toolkit.

Figure 5. Kolb's [30] Triple E model.

Disadvantages and Limitations

- Subjective interpretation: Since the framework relies on educators' judgment to evaluate the impact of technology, its application can vary between individuals, leading to inconsistent results.
- Limited scope: The model is designed specifically for K-12 educators, though it may be adaptable to other educational settings. It focuses primarily on short-term lesson planning and may not be as effective for long-term technology integration strategies.
- Lacks a progression path: The framework does not provide a clear route for advancing from basic to more advanced technology use, which could make it harder for teachers to see how they can evolve their practices over time.
- Misses broader competencies: It does not explicitly outline the necessary skills educators must develop to use technology effectively in the classroom, nor does it account for different types of technology such as XR.
- Narrow focus on the tool's impact: The model focuses primarily on how technology affects students' learning without delving into what students themselves do or the prerequisite competencies they need to learn effectively with technology.
- Instructional strategies are suggestions: While the model recommends strategies, it does not offer a comprehensive prescriptive guide for how to implement them.

Overall, the Triple E framework serves as a highly usable tool for educators seeking to integrate technology in a purposeful way that enhances student learning. However, its

narrow focus on individual lessons and lack of detailed guidance for long-term planning or diverse technological tools may limit its utility in broader educational contexts.

3.1.6. DigCompEdu Model: Digital Competencies for Educators

The *European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators* (DigCompEdu), developed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission [31], originates from the growing need to equip educators with the digital skills required to integrate technology effectively in education. This framework draws on existing digital competence models, notably the European Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp) [32], and synthesizes various national and regional efforts to define digital competencies specific to educators. It was established to provide a cohesive structure that educators can use to evaluate and develop their digital pedagogical skills, fostering innovative and inclusive teaching and learning practices across Europe.

Structurally, the framework is organized into six distinct areas that cover different aspects of educators' professional activities (see Figure 6): *professional engagement*, *digital resources*, *teaching and learning*, *assessment*, *empowering learners*, and *facilitating learners' digital competence*. These areas encompass a total of 22 specific competences, ranging from the use of digital technologies in communication and collaboration to the creation of digital learning resources, the orchestration of digital learning strategies, and the facilitation of learners' own digital competencies. In addition to this, the framework proposes a progression model with six proficiency levels, from *newcomer* (A1) to *pioneer* (C2), providing a clear path for educators to develop their digital competence over time.

Figure 6. Areas within Redecker's [31] DigCompEdu model.

In terms of practical application, DigCompEdu is a usable tool for teachers at various educational levels, from early childhood to higher education. Its proficiency model allows educators to engage with the framework according to their current skill level, making it accessible for both beginners and advanced users. Nonetheless, it may miss the mark for educators operating in under-resourced settings, where the availability of digital tools and training opportunities may be limited. Additionally, the framework emphasizes individual competencies, but does not sufficiently account for the collaborative and institutional changes required to fully embed digital technologies in education.

The DigCompEdu framework is highly versatile, allowing it to be used as a reference point for policymakers, educational institutions, and training providers aiming to boost

educators' digital skills. It supports professional development by identifying educators' specific training needs and guiding the integration of digital tools into pedagogy. The framework's structured approach ensures educators can systematically develop their skills in using technology to enhance both teaching and learning. The framework is well-suited to answering questions related to how educators can integrate digital technologies into their teaching strategies, how they can support learner autonomy, and how digital tools can facilitate more personalized learning. It provides insight into how digital competence evolves, offering educators clarity on their current skill levels and the next steps for their development.

However, while DigCompEdu offers several advantages, such as a comprehensive and adaptable model, it also has certain limitations. For example, the framework may fall short when addressing broader systemic issues, such as digital equity and access to resources, which are not explicitly incorporated into its structure. The model particularly falls short when it comes to addressing the rapidly evolving field of XR. The framework does not explicitly account for the unique competencies required to effectively integrate XR technologies into educational practices. XR environments present new pedagogical challenges that go beyond traditional digital resources, such as the need for spatial awareness, 3D content creation, and the ability to design immersive learning experiences that are interactive and highly contextualized.

DigCompEdu primarily focuses on conventional digital tools and strategies, such as online platforms, digital content, and collaboration tools, which do not fully encompass the immersive and experiential nature of XR. Educators working with XR need to develop specific skills in handling immersive environments, which include understanding the cognitive and emotional impacts of VR or AR on learners, navigating virtual spaces, and managing potential technical difficulties, such as hardware compatibility and latency issues. The current framework does not sufficiently address these technical and pedagogical complexities.

Furthermore, the framework lacks guidance on how to evaluate the effectiveness of XR-based learning, which often requires different assessment strategies than those used for traditional digital technologies. For instance, in XR, learners can engage in simulation-based tasks that involve high levels of interaction and problem solving in real time, demanding new forms of assessment that focus on experiential learning outcomes rather than the more static metrics of traditional digital content. The framework's limited treatment of innovative assessment approaches thus makes it less useful for educators seeking to adopt XR tools.

Finally, DigCompEdu does not consider the ethical and safety concerns that arise with the use of XR in education, such as issues related to data privacy, the psychological effects of immersive environments, and ensuring equitable access to these technologies for all learners. As XR technologies become more widespread, educators will need to understand how to manage these risks; yet, the framework does not provide specific competencies in these areas. Therefore, while DigCompEdu is a strong foundation for describing general digital competencies, it is currently insufficient to fully prepare educators for the challenges and opportunities presented by XR.

3.1.7. Summary of Properties of XR Enabling Educational Activities

Above, we have discussed various models and the advantages and disadvantages of these models for implementing XR in education. Below, we summarize the properties of XR, which can be derived from these models and frameworks. This summary was created by considering what features of XR emerge in these models/frameworks that provide support for learning activities organized with XR.

Immersion

XR technologies create fully immersive learning environments that engage multiple senses. This deep level of immersion is crucial for simulating real-world scenarios and abstract concepts, making learning more intuitive and impactful. For example, VR can transport students to historical sites or inside a human body, providing a visceral learning experience that textbooks cannot replicate.

Interactivity

Interactivity is a core feature of XR, allowing students and educators to manipulate their environment and receive real-time feedback. This property is essential for activities such as virtual labs or interactive simulations where learners can experiment and see the effects of their actions instantly, enhancing understanding and retention.

Adaptability

XR environments can be dynamically adjusted to suit the educational needs and learning pace of individual students. This adaptability makes it possible to personalize learning experiences to different abilities and needs, supporting differentiated instruction and personalized learning paths.

Connectivity

XR facilitates connectivity, enabling collaborative learning experiences regardless of geographical constraints. Students can work together in the same virtual space from different locations, fostering teamwork and communication skills. This is particularly useful for group projects and collaborative problem-solving tasks.

Scalability

XR technologies are scalable, allowing for the creation of learning modules that can be expanded and adapted for different levels of complexity and for varying numbers of participants. This scalability ensures that XR can be integrated into different educational settings, from small classrooms to large-scale online courses.

Accessibility

Enhanced accessibility is another significant feature of XR. These technologies can be designed to include accessible learning experiences for students with disabilities, such as providing auditory descriptions for the visually impaired or sign language for the deaf. XR's adaptability in accessibility settings ensures that all students have equal opportunities to learn and engage.

Real-Time Assessment and Feedback

XR supports real-time assessment and feedback mechanisms. Educators can monitor interactions within XR environments to assess student understanding and provide immediate personalized feedback. This ongoing assessment helps tailor instruction to meet learners' needs more effectively.

Data Integration

XR systems can integrate various data streams, providing educators with detailed insights into student performance and engagement. This integration supports evidence-informed practices and allows for continuous adjustment of teaching strategies based on real-time data.

The aforementioned properties of XR technologies not only facilitate a broad range of educational activities, but also transform the teaching and learning landscape into a

more engaging, effective, and inclusive environment. These enhancements are crucial for preparing both educators and students to thrive in a digitally augmented world.

3.2. Results Relating to Research Question 2: XR-Related Digital Competencies for Educators

As was expected beforehand, the DigCompEdu model emerged as the framework that most concretely addresses the competencies teachers need when teaching with XR. Other frameworks touch on this only marginally. Therefore, for answering research question 2, we decided to expand the DigCompEdu framework. This section is organized according to its categorization of domains: *professional engagement, digital resources, teaching and learning, assessment, empowering learners, and facilitating learners' digital competence*. By integrating XR technologies, we highlight the enhancements that range from enriching professional development to transforming student assessment and engagement. XR-based learning activities have been formulated. For each competence, the main differences from the original DigCompEdu framework are highlighted with practical examples. The complete cards can be found in Appendix A (and are accessible via the provided links).

3.2.1. Area 1: Professional Engagement

In the realm of professional engagement, XR technologies offer transformative opportunities for educators to enhance teaching, communication, and professional development. They provide immersive interactive experiences that extend the capabilities of traditional digital tools, including virtual meetings and discussions, which become more engaging and accessible, and the simulation of real-world scenarios for hands-on experience without physical constraints.

Organizational Communication (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduOc>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework focuses on delivering information through standard digital channels, the XR-based approach introduces virtual environments for activities like open days, meetings, and progress reports, offering more engaging and dynamic communication. For instance, a virtual open day powered by XR allows prospective students and parents to interactively explore educational facilities, creating a more impactful experience than traditional methods.

Professional Collaboration (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduPc>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

The original framework emphasizes asynchronous collaboration and resource sharing, whereas the XR extension enables real-time collaboration in shared 3D virtual spaces. Educators can co-create, manipulate educational materials, and engage in immersive experiential learning. This approach removes geographical constraints, facilitating global collaboration through virtual exchange programs.

Reflective Practice (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduRp>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

XR allows teachers to record and review their sessions from multiple perspectives, simulate challenging scenarios, and experiment with pedagogical strategies in virtual environments. XR-based mentorship and peer-to-peer coaching further support collaborative reflection and safe experimentation, thereby enhancing professional growth.

Digital Continuous Professional Development (CPD) (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduDCPD>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework emphasizes online self-directed learning and participation in professional communities, the XR extension offers immersive hands-on learning via

virtual simulations and workshops. For example, instead of passively watching tutorials, a science teacher might use XR to practice laboratory techniques in a fully immersive virtual lab, thereby enhancing both skill development and practical application.

3.2.2. Area 2: Digital Resources

XR technologies require educators to develop sophisticated competencies in selecting, creating, modifying, and managing digital resources. These activities involve critically evaluating XR tools to ensure they align with educational goals and accessibility standards.

Selecting Digital Resources (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduSdr>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework focuses on selecting traditional digital content like videos or websites, the XR extension expands this to include immersive XR resources. Teachers must evaluate factors such as interactivity, sensory accessibility, scalability, and integration with existing infrastructures. For example, instead of selecting credible websites for a history lesson, an educator might choose a VR application that allows students to interactively explore ancient Roman architecture.

Creating and Modifying Digital Resources (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduCamdr>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

The original framework emphasizes creating static or interactive 2D resources, whereas the XR extension focuses on designing immersive multisensory learning environments. Key aspects include integrating interactive elements, collaboratively developing XR resources, and ensuring ethical sharing via XR-specific licensing. For instance, a teacher might develop an immersive VR simulation of the circulatory system that allows students to explore 3D models interactively.

Managing, Protecting, and Sharing Digital Resources (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduMpasdr>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework deals with sharing traditional materials through basic platforms, the XR extension necessitates using specialized platforms for securely sharing immersive content. This involves managing complex permissions, enforcing copyright with DRM tools, and addressing ethical considerations related to sensitive XR content. For example, in an XR-based biology lesson, a teacher would ensure compliance with privacy and licensing regulations while managing student access.

3.2.3. Area 3: Teaching and Learning

The integration of XR into *teaching and learning* transforms education by creating dynamic and personalized learning experiences. By leveraging virtual and augmented realities, educators can simulate complex scenarios that foster deeper understanding and student engagement.

Teaching (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduT>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework relies on digital tools, like whiteboards and mobile devices, the XR extension leverages immersive technologies to create interactive learning environments. These environments, which include 3D simulations and virtual field trips, provide real-time feedback and enable innovative pedagogical approaches. For instance, a chemistry instructor may employ XR technologies to enable students to interact with three-dimensional molecular models, thereby significantly deepening their comprehension of complex structures.

Guidance (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduG>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

The XR extension enhances guidance by offering immersive, real-time, and adaptive support beyond traditional digital tools. Educators can provide immediate contextual assistance in virtual environments, use AR for step-by-step task guidance, and design adaptive tutorials. For example, in medical training, XR enables educators to guide students through virtual surgeries, offering tailored feedback based on real-time performance.

Collaborative Learning (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduCl>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework uses blogs, wikis, and learning management systems for collaboration, the XR extension leverages immersive environments where learners can interact in real time. In these settings, students can manipulate virtual objects and participate in role-playing simulations to solve complex problems. For instance, an XR-based climate change simulation may allow students to collaboratively manipulate ecosystems and experience the impact of their decisions.

Self-Regulated Learning (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduSrl>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

The original framework supports self-regulated learning through tools like blogs and ePortfolios, whereas the XR extension enriches this by offering immersive experiences. Learners can design personalized learning paths, gather evidence via 3D simulations, and engage in reflective practices using interactive journals. For example, students studying ecosystems might use XR to explore virtual environments and document their progress in real time.

3.2.4. Area 4: Assessment

XR technologies enhance the realism and interactivity of assessments by simulating real-world applications. They offer diverse assessment opportunities, from virtual laboratories to interactive historical scenarios, that provide continuous performance tracking and real-time feedback.

Assessment Strategies (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduAs>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework relies on quizzes and ePortfolios, XR enables assessments in realistic simulated scenarios. Students demonstrate their skills by interacting with virtual environments, yielding deeper insights into their abilities and decision-making processes. Tailored experiences, such as virtual labs or reenactments, offer a comprehensive evaluation of student learning outcomes.

Analyzing Evidence (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduAe>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

The XR extension enhances data analysis by leveraging immersive technologies to capture detailed datasets, tracking behaviors, gaze patterns, and decision making in VR/AR environments. Advanced visualization tools allow educators to represent complex learning data intuitively while integrating XR analytics with conventional data sources to provide a holistic view of learner progress. For example, in a medical education setting, VR simulations can enable personalized adaptive teaching strategies based on real-time behavioral data.

Feedback and Planning (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduFap>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

XR technologies enable contextual feedback within simulations, support real-time progress tracking, and offer adaptive learning based on immediate learner actions. They foster personalized learning experiences through tailored virtual scenarios and facilitate collaborative reflection and planning.

3.2.5. Area 5: Empowering Learners

XR technologies offer transformative potential by enhancing educational accessibility, personalization, and active engagement. They create immersive adaptive learning environments that respond to individual needs, simulating inaccessible real-world scenarios and supporting multisensory learning with real-time adaptations.

Accessibility and Inclusion (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduAai>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

Unlike the original framework, which emphasizes equitable access to digital tools, the XR extension enables students to engage with virtual environments that simulate real-world scenarios. For example, VR can simulate inaccessible locations for mobility-impaired students, while AR provides visual or auditory enhancements tailored to individual needs. Additionally, tools such as language translation and sign language support foster greater inclusivity.

Differentiation and Personalization (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduDap>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

Whereas the original framework uses digital tools to create varied learning paths, the XR extension leverages VR and AR to design dynamic interactive environments that adjust in real time to students' progress. This approach offers personalized challenges for high achievers and tailored support for learners with specific needs. For instance, in a biology class, students might explore human anatomy in VR, with tasks dynamically adjusted based on their performance, while AR provides individualized guidance.

Actively Engaging Learners (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduAel>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework uses animations, videos, and quizzes for engagement, the XR extension employs immersive 3D models, simulations, and virtual environments that allow learners to interact directly with complex concepts. XR enables hands-on experiences such as virtual labs and role plays, significantly enhancing active learning outcomes.

Area 6: Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence

XR technologies play a significant role in developing learners' digital competence by providing immersive, interactive environments that help visualize complex data, interact with digital overlays, and engage in simulated scenarios.

Information and Media Literacy (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduIaml>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework emphasizes critical analysis and structured information management, the XR extension introduces dynamic tools that allow learners to explore abstract concepts via 3D simulations and real-time data interactions. For example, students might use VR to navigate a virtual heart or AR to visualize the cardiovascular system, thereby enhancing their understanding.

Digital Communication and Collaboration (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduDcac>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

The original framework relies on traditional platforms for communication and collaboration, whereas the XR extension leverages virtual environments to simulate real-world interactions. This includes VR-based role playing, AR-enhanced projects, and MR discussions that bridge cultural and generational gaps. For instance, a global studies class might

use VR to simulate diplomatic negotiations, enhancing cross-cultural communication and problem-solving skills.

Digital Content Creation (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduDcc>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

XR-based activities emphasize multidimensional content creation within immersive environments. For example, in a biology class, students might collaboratively design a 3D virtual anatomy model using VR, supplemented with AR layers to simulate biological processes, while a teacher guides them through the technical and ethical aspects.

Responsible Use (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduRu>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

While the original framework emphasizes data protection and cyberbullying prevention, the XR extension focuses on ethical conduct in immersive spaces, including privacy management involving avatars and addressing health risks like VR-induced motion sickness. For example, a history teacher using XR must guide students in protecting their digital identities and ensure respectful interactions through enhanced monitoring tools.

Digital Problem Solving (<http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduDps>, Accessed on 24 January 2025)

The original framework focuses on troubleshooting general digital tools, but the XR extension emphasizes diagnosing and optimizing XR-specific hardware and software. Educators must customize immersive interfaces to meet individual learning needs and use XR to simulate complex real-world problems. For example, a teacher using a VR-based chemistry lab enables students to experiment with hazardous materials safely while also troubleshooting technical issues and fostering collaborative problem solving.

3.2.6. Common Points and Contradictions

Across the XR-related digital competencies, several common themes emerge. Immersive real-time interactivity, experiential learning, and adaptive environments are central to domains such as professional engagement, teaching and learning, and collaborative learning. However, notable contradictions arise among these XR competencies. For example, while immersive environments foster open, dynamic, and collaborative interactions, they simultaneously demand robust ethical safeguards and controlled settings—as emphasized in responsible use and digital problem solving—to manage risks such as privacy breaches and adverse health effects. Similarly, the drive for personalization and adaptive learning in areas like self-regulated learning and differentiation can conflict with the need for standardized assessment strategies and comprehensive data analytics, which require consistency and structure. These tensions underscore the challenge of balancing the transformative potential of XR—enabling unprecedented interactivity and immediacy—with the equally critical need for secure, ethical, and analytically rigorous educational environments.

3.3. Expert Member Check

To evaluate the alignment between the developed teacher competencies in XR and the practical observations of experts, an expert member check was conducted during a live meeting of the PAX project on 7 October 2024 in Olomouc, Czech Republic. Sixteen consortium members from Austria, the Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, and Slovenia attended this session. The group comprised a diverse mix of professionals, including full and associate professors specializing in digital pedagogy and competence development and researchers and practitioners with expertise in XR design and applications in STEM and vocational contexts, as well as experienced project managers known for leading complex educational innovation initiatives. This multidisciplinary composition

ensured that the validation process was both transparent and robust, drawing on insights from academic research as well as practical implementation perspectives.

During the session, the experts provided extensive and detailed feedback on the framework. For example, one participant observed that, although the card delineating teaching competencies was comprehensive, it appeared to neglect the incorporation of XR to promote empathetic learning. In our framework, the corresponding learning activities aim to enhance student engagement and understanding through simulations of real-world scenarios, a strategy that implicitly supports empathetic learning. Another expert pointed out that, although accessibility was discussed, a broader exploration was needed. This included not only the technical understanding of the medium, but also ensuring that the needs of learners with disabilities are fully addressed. For this purpose, however, the *accessibility and inclusion* competency was designed to incorporate learning activities specifically aimed at accommodating a diverse range of physical, sensory, and cognitive needs.

Additional comments emphasized the importance of maintaining a balance between pedagogical and technical skills. This balance is reflected in the framework through several competencies, including those focused on digital resources as well as *Teaching* and learning. Ethical concerns were also raised, prompting us to integrate explicit learning activities under the *Responsible use* competency. These activities focus on educating learners about ethical practices in XR and ensuring integrity in virtual interactions. Moreover, hygiene issues—such as managing specific health risks associated with prolonged XR use—were incorporated into the same competency.

Some experts suggested that the framework could benefit from offering both a detailed version and a more accessible simplified version. Although the current article elaborates only on the detailed version, it provides a solid foundation for developing a simpler version in the future. There were also recommendations to differentiate the competencies according to expertise levels (novice, intermediate, expert) and to tailor them to different target groups, such as teachers versus teacher trainers. While these refinements have not yet been implemented, they represent promising avenues for future development.

A number of experts observed that the model, while robust, might be perceived as too general. They proposed the inclusion of more XR-specific sub-competencies—for example, skills related to navigating and interacting within 3D spaces—to sharpen the framework's focus. In the present version, elements such as spatial awareness are partially addressed within the competency dedicated to actively engaging learners through interactive 3D models and simulations.

Furthermore, the concept of teaching through embodied cognition emerged as a critical area for enhancement. Although XR inherently supports embodied learning [33], this aspect was initially under-represented in the framework. Consequently, a new card specifically addressing embodied cognition has been added: <http://bit.ly/XRDigCompEduEl>. Similarly, the idea of “presence” in the XR classroom was discussed. This is already reflected within the *Digital communication and collaboration* competency, which emphasizes understanding the nuances of presence and representation in virtual communities.

Other practical challenges—such as supervising a VR classroom remotely, designing XR-based learning scenarios, and managing classroom resources including hardware—were also addressed. These issues have been integrated, respectively, into the *Guidance*, *Creating and modifying digital resources*, and *Digital problem solving* competencies.

In summary, the expert member check provided critical insights that have significantly refined the teacher competencies framework for XR. This feedback process has ensured that our framework is both theoretically grounded and practically relevant, setting the stage for future enhancements.

4. Conclusions

This study aimed to assess the suitability of existing pedagogical frameworks for integrating XR into educational contexts and to identify the specific competencies required for the effective implementation of XR-based teaching. Our discussion of established models—including TPACK, TIM, SAMR, CAMIL, and DigCompEdu—revealed that, while these frameworks offer important insights into technology integration, they often lack the nuance needed to address the unique affordances and challenges of XR environments [7,10].

Building on these insights, the DigCompEdu model was extended to integrate XR-specific competencies tailored to the distinct requirements of immersive educational environments. This extension comprises clearly defined components addressing immersive resource creation, spatial awareness, and embodied cognition, as well as the ethical and technical aspects associated with managing real-time data within immersive settings. Our proposed framework was refined and validated through an expert member check involving diverse practitioners across Europe, confirming that these competencies better capture the demands of XR-supported teaching compared to more traditional models [6,11].

The practical implications of our findings are twofold. First, by articulating a set of XR-specific competencies, our study provides educators with a concrete and evidence-based roadmap for professional development. This roadmap emphasizes not only the need for technical proficiency, but also the importance of reflective pedagogical practices and ethical considerations in immersive environments. Second, our findings highlight the critical need for sustained experiential training and structured collaborative learning opportunities, particularly in light of the continuous evolution of XR technologies.

In conclusion, the extended framework reconciles general digital competence models with the specific requirements of XR within educational settings. Future research should examine the long-term impact of these competencies on teaching outcomes and explore adaptations of the framework across diverse educational contexts. By grounding our approach in both the contemporary literature and practical expert feedback, this study offers a robust foundation for educators and policymakers striving to harness the transformative potential of XR in education.

5. Discussion

To ensure the quality and trustworthiness of this study, several measures were implemented. First, the triangulation of data sources through the integration of desk research and expert feedback enhanced the credibility of our findings. In addition, systematic documentation was maintained by applying the explicit literature selection criteria and detailing the refinement process, thereby bolstering the dependability and confirmability of this research. The expert member check further validated the findings by confirming that the developed competencies accurately reflect real-world practices and needs. However, some limitations must be acknowledged. The reliance on Google Scholar may have led to the omission of relevant studies not indexed in this database. Moreover, the expert panel's predominantly European composition could restrict the transferability of the findings to other geographical or educational contexts. Finally, given that the experts were already familiar with XR practices, there is a potential for confirmation bias, which might have reinforced pre-existing assumptions. Future research should consider diversifying data sources and expanding the expert panel to include a broader range of stakeholders, thereby enhancing the generalizability and robustness of the findings.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Appendix A

The card set that resulted from the methods applied in this study is included in full in this appendix.

Table A1. Competency: Organizational communication.

1. To utilize XR technologies to create immersive interactive experiences for virtual open days and informational events, allowing learners and parents to explore educational facilities and resources in a virtual environment.
2. To deploy XR platforms for conducting virtual meetings and discussions with parents and learners, providing a more engaging and interactive communication experience compared to traditional digital methods.
3. To implement XR systems to provide real-time immersive updates about learners' progress and issues of concern, enabling parents and educators to experience educational scenarios or challenges through virtual simulations.
4. To use XR tools to facilitate virtual collaboration among colleagues within the same organization and with external partners, enhancing the sharing of ideas and strategies through interactive 3D virtual environments.
5. To integrate XR in training sessions for educators and staff, simulating real-world educational challenges and scenarios, thereby improving communication skills and strategies under varied conditions.
6. To employ XR technology to create detailed virtual tours of educational events, field trips, or external locations linked to the curriculum, making them accessible to learners and external stakeholders to enhance their understanding of the educational context and content.

Table A2. Competency: Professional collaboration.

1. To utilize XR platforms to co-create and inhabit shared virtual spaces for real-time collaboration on educational projects, allowing educators to interact with and manipulate educational materials in a 3D environment.
2. To employ XR technology to simulate classroom environments, enabling educators to share and demonstrate pedagogical techniques and classroom management strategies in a controlled virtual setting.
3. To develop virtual reality workshops and seminars where educators can experience and discuss new pedagogical practices in immersive environments, enhancing understanding through experiential learning.
4. To use XR tools for role playing and scenario-based training, helping educators practice and refine teaching strategies and interpersonal skills with peers in a virtual risk-free environment.
5. To facilitate access to international professional collaborative networks through virtual exchange programs, allowing educators to observe and interact with teaching practices and educational systems different from their own without geographical constraints.

Table A3. Competency: Reflective practice.

1. To use XR technologies to record and review one's own teaching sessions in a virtual environment, allowing educators to critically analyze their interactions and pedagogical approaches from multiple perspectives.
2. To implement VR simulations that mirror challenging teaching scenarios to identify personal competence gaps and areas for improvement, providing a safe space to experiment with different strategies.
3. To participate in virtual reality coaching sessions or mentorship programs where more experienced educators can guide less experienced ones in improving their digital and pedagogical skills through immersive hands-on practice.
4. To engage in virtual professional development workshops and courses that utilize XR to provide deep immersive learning experiences focused on cutting-edge digital pedagogical practices.
5. To create and participate in collaborative XR environments for peer-to-peer coaching sessions where educators can help each other develop digital pedagogical competencies by sharing experiences and feedback in an engaging interactive format.
6. To use XR tools at the organizational level to simulate the impact of different digital policies and practices on teaching and learning, providing a virtual sandbox for policy experimentation and feedback collection.
7. To contribute to the development of organizational practices by using XR to prototype and evaluate new digital technologies and their integration into pedagogical strategies, ensuring they align with educational goals and standards.

Table A4. Competency: Digital Continuous Professional Development (CPD).

1. To utilize XR platforms to access immersive training modules and simulations that offer experiential learning opportunities in subject-specific competences, allowing educators to apply theoretical knowledge in virtual practical scenarios.
2. To engage in virtual reality environments that showcase innovative pedagogical methods and strategies, providing educators with a hands-on way to explore and adopt new teaching techniques in a controlled immersive setting.
3. To use XR technologies to participate in interactive virtual conferences and professional workshops, enabling real-time collaboration and learning from experts in the field without geographical limitations.
4. To explore virtual professional development libraries and repositories that include XR-based resources, enhancing the discovery and utilization of digital tools and content that support ongoing professional growth.
5. To participate in and contribute to virtual communities of practice using XR, where educators can share, discuss, and develop new digital pedagogical practices in immersive collaborative environments.
6. To design and deliver XR-based training sessions for peers, leveraging virtual and augmented reality to create dynamic and engaging learning experiences that illustrate complex concepts or procedures clearly and effectively.
7. To use XR to create role play and simulation experiences for professional development, allowing educators to practice and refine teaching and managerial skills in a realistic yet risk-free virtual environment.

Table A5. Competency: Selecting digital resources.

1. To explore and evaluate immersive digital resources for XR environments, teachers should develop strategies to find and assess immersive XR content that can be integrated into teaching and learning, ensuring the resources align with the educational objectives and enhance the learning experience.
2. To select XR resources that offer interactive and immersive experiences, teachers should choose XR applications and content that provide students with interactive and immersive learning opportunities tailored to the specific needs of the students.

Table A5. *Cont.*

3. To critically assess the technological and sensory accessibility of XR resources, teachers must evaluate XR resources not only for content quality, but also for accessibility, ensuring that these resources can be used by all students, including those with sensory or motor impairments.
4. To determine the alignment of XR resources with pedagogical goals, it is crucial to assess how well XR tools and content support the pedagogical approaches adopted for different subjects and learning outcomes, fostering engagement and deeper understanding.
5. To evaluate the scalability and integration capability of XR tools in existing digital environments, teachers should consider the technical requirements and compatibility of XR tools with existing digital infrastructures in educational settings, ensuring seamless integration and scalability.

Table A6. Competency: Creating and modifying digital resources.

1. To design and develop immersive XR learning environments, teachers should be equipped to create immersive virtual or augmented reality spaces that provide students with interactive and engaging learning experiences tailored to the educational objectives and learning context.
2. To modify existing XR environments to better suit pedagogical needs, teachers should learn to adjust and personalize existing XR content, ensuring that it aligns with specific learning goals and the needs of diverse student groups.
3. To collaborate in the creation of shared XR projects, teachers should be encouraged to work together with peers or experts in technology to develop collaborative XR learning projects that can be used across different educational settings and disciplines.
4. To incorporate interactive elements into XR resources, teachers should be adept at integrating interactive components like quizzes, simulations, or problem-solving tasks into XR environments to enhance engagement and learning efficacy.
5. To ensure XR content adheres to accessibility and usability standards, it is essential for teachers to consider the accessibility of XR resources, ensuring they are usable by all students, including those with disabilities, by incorporating adjustable settings, alternative inputs, and multisensory outputs.
6. To understand and apply XR-specific licensing and intellectual property rules, teachers need to be aware of the specific licensing issues related to XR content to ensure legal compliance and ethical use of digital materials in educational contexts.

Table A7. Competency: Managing, protecting, and sharing digital resources.

1. To securely share XR resources through specialized platforms and services, educators should learn to utilize XR-specific platforms or secure cloud services that support the sharing of large-format and interactive XR content, maintaining high standards of data security and user privacy.
2. To manage access to XR environments with consideration for educational roles and data privacy, teachers should be adept at setting permissions and managing access to XR resources, ensuring that only relevant stakeholders (students, educators, parents) have appropriate access based on their educational roles and privacy considerations.
3. To use digital rights management (DRM) tools for XR content to enforce copyright and licensing rules, educators need to implement DRM solutions for XR resources to protect intellectual property rights and ensure compliance with licensing agreements.
4. To attribute XR-specific licenses and understand the implications of XR content creation and distribution, it is important for teachers to apply and understand licenses that are suitable for XR resources, which may involve more complex rights management due to the immersive and interactive nature of the content.
5. To implement strategies for the protection of sensitive information within XR platforms, teachers must employ strategies to protect sensitive data, such as student performance metrics or personal information, especially when such data is embedded in interactive and potentially publicly accessible XR environments.
6. To educate students and colleagues on the ethical use and sharing of XR resources, awareness and understanding should be promoted among educators and students about the ethical considerations and best practices for using and sharing XR resources, particularly focusing on issues related to copyright, privacy, and data integrity.

Table A8. Competency: Teaching.

1. To integrate XR technologies to create immersive and interactive learning environments that enhance student engagement and understanding by simulating real-world scenarios and abstract concepts in virtual and augmented realities.
2. To design and implement XR-supported lessons that enable students to interact with 3D models and simulations, facilitating a deeper understanding of complex subjects and fostering active learning.
3. To utilize XR for differentiated instruction by tailoring learning experiences to meet diverse learning needs and preferences in a virtual or augmented environment, allowing for the personalization of pace and complexity.
4. To manage and facilitate collaborative learning through XR platforms, where students can work together in virtual environments from different physical locations, enhancing communication skills and teamwork.
5. To employ XR tools for real-time assessment and feedback, where educators can monitor students' interactions within virtual environments to assess understanding and provide immediate personalized feedback.
6. To reflect on and adapt XR integration in teaching practices by evaluating the effectiveness of XR technologies in achieving learning objectives and adjusting instructional strategies accordingly.
7. To explore and develop innovative pedagogical approaches using XR technologies, such as virtual field trips, role-playing simulations, and interactive storytelling, to enhance experiential learning.

Table A9. Competency: Guidance.

1. To employ XR platforms for immediate and immersive guidance, enabling educators to enter virtual environments with learners to provide direct contextual support and clarification on tasks or concepts.
2. To design XR-guided tutorials and interactive simulations, which automatically adjust to individual learners' progress and provide real-time tailored feedback and guidance based on their interactions and decisions within the virtual environment.
3. To utilize augmented reality overlays for guidance in real-world tasks by providing step-by-step augmented instructions or corrections that appear in the learner's field of view, enhancing practical learning and skill acquisition.
4. To create collaborative XR environments for peer guidance, where learners can support each other's learning processes through shared virtual spaces, promoting peer-to-peer learning and collaboration.
5. To monitor and analyze learner interactions within XR settings by using advanced tracking and analytics to understand learner behavior and provide targeted interventions that foster self-regulated learning.
6. To experiment with multimodal feedback systems in XR, integrating visual, auditory, and haptic feedback to guide learners effectively and inclusively, accommodating diverse learning needs.
7. To develop personalized learning journeys within immersive environments, allowing learners to explore guided learning paths that adapt to their individual pace, enhancing engagement and mastery over complex subjects.

Table A10. Competency: Collaborative learning.

1. To implement collaborative XR projects, where learners can interact within a shared virtual or augmented reality environment to undertake group tasks, simulate real-world scenarios, or solve problems together.
2. To utilize XR platforms for role playing and simulations, allowing learners to assume different roles within a virtual world to understand perspectives and solve collaborative challenges that mimic real-life situations.
3. To design XR environments for dynamic knowledge construction, where learners can build and manipulate virtual objects or datasets in real time, fostering collaborative exploration and discovery.
4. To facilitate synchronous and asynchronous collaborative learning in XR, enabling interactions through avatars or digital representations in real time, as well as through recorded sessions that learners can revisit and learn from collaboratively.
5. To use augmented reality for enhancing real-world collaboration by overlaying digital information on physical objects and environments, which can be manipulated collectively by learners during tasks or projects.
6. To employ XR tools for virtual peer assessment and feedback, where learners can give and receive feedback on collaborative tasks directly within the virtual environment, enhancing reflection and self-regulation.
7. To explore and develop new XR-driven pedagogical methods for collaborative learning, such as collaborative virtual labs, joint virtual field trips, or multiplayer educational games that require team strategy and decision making.

Table A11. Competency: Self-regulated learning.

1. To implement XR tools for personalized learning planning, enabling learners to design and navigate their own learning paths in immersive virtual environments that adapt to their progress and preferences.
2. To use XR technologies to create interactive learning diaries and journals, where learners can record and reflect on their learning experiences through virtual reality experiences or augmented reality overlays, enhancing the depth of reflection and retention.
3. To employ XR for dynamic evidence collection, allowing learners to capture and review their progress and achievements in a virtual or augmented reality format, including 3D models, simulations, and virtual project outcomes.
4. To integrate ePortfolios in XR, enabling learners to compile and display their work within a virtual gallery or interactive space that showcases their academic and creative achievements in a multidimensional environment.
5. To develop reflective practices through immersive simulations in XR, where learners can revisit their actions or decisions in a virtual space to assess outcomes and understand the impact of different choices, fostering deeper self-assessment and learning insights.
6. To utilize AR for real-time feedback and guidance by overlaying information or corrections directly into the learner's field of view, providing instant feedback that aids in self-assessment and learning adjustments.
7. To create virtual environments for experimenting with self-regulated learning strategies, allowing learners to test and develop their learning techniques in controlled yet flexible and responsive virtual settings.

Table A12. Competency: Assessment strategies.

1. To use XR technologies to create immersive assessment environments: Implement virtual reality (VR) or augmented reality (AR) scenarios that simulate real-world applications of subject matter, allowing for practical assessments of skills and knowledge in a controlled yet realistic environment.
2. To employ XR for dynamic formative assessments: Utilize AR to overlay real-time data and feedback on students' physical work, enabling immediate corrections and adjustments. Similarly, VR can be used to engage students in complex problem-solving situations where their decisions and actions can be tracked and assessed continuously.
3. To integrate XR in summative assessments: Develop VR-based exams where students interact with virtual objects or environments to perform tasks that demonstrate their understanding and mastery of content, providing a deeper insight into their practical skills beyond traditional testing formats.
4. To use XR to support diverse assessment strategies: Offer multiple XR-based assessment paths to accommodate different learning needs, such as virtual labs for science students, virtual field trips for geography students, or interactive historical reenactments for history students.
5. To critically evaluate the effectiveness of XR in assessment: Regularly review and analyze the impact of XR technologies on student outcomes, adjusting approaches to leverage strengths and address any emerging challenges in XR-based assessments.

Table A13. Competency: Analyzing evidence.

1. To utilize XR technologies to generate rich datasets on learner interactions and behaviors: Implement VR and AR scenarios that are designed to track a wide range of learner interactions, such as gaze tracking, movement analysis, and decision-making processes, providing a more nuanced understanding of learner engagement and performance.
2. To employ XR tools for enhanced visualization of learning data: Use AR to overlay statistical data and analytics on learners' physical environments, or use VR to create dynamic 3D data visualizations, helping educators and learners alike visualize complex data in intuitive and accessible ways.
3. To analyze learner behavior in immersive environments: Utilize the detailed data collected from XR interactions to analyze and understand learner behaviors under simulated conditions, enhancing the ability to tailor learning experiences to individual needs.
4. To integrate data from XR experiences with traditional learning analytics: Combine the unique datasets obtained from XR environments with traditional educational data sources, such as e-portfolios and learning management systems, to provide a comprehensive view of learner progress and performance.
5. To critically assess the validity and reliability of data from XR sources: Regularly evaluate the accuracy and relevance of the data collected through XR technologies, ensuring that it effectively informs teaching and learning decisions without compromising educational integrity.
6. To innovate with XR to support evidence-informed educational practices: Continuously explore new ways XR can contribute to evidence-based teaching strategies, ensuring that the use of such technology is aligned with educational goals and enhances learning outcomes.

Table A14. Competency: Feedback and planning.

1. To use XR technologies to provide immersive feedback on assignments: Implement virtual reality environments where learners can receive contextual interactive feedback directly within the simulation, offering a visual and experiential understanding of corrections, suggestions, and improvements.
2. To incorporate AR for real-time feedback and progress monitoring: Utilize augmented reality to overlay feedback on physical assignments, allowing learners to see corrections and comments in context with their original work, enhancing comprehension and retention.
3. To employ XR tools for continuous assessment and adaptive learning support: Develop VR or AR applications that track learner progress and adapt in real time, providing personalized prompts and support based on the learner's immediate actions and needs.
4. To use XR to simulate and revise teaching practices based on learner data: Create virtual classrooms in VR where teachers can simulate and revise different teaching and assessment strategies, analyzing the virtual learners' responses to refine approaches before applying them in the real classroom.
5. To offer differentiated XR experiences for personalized learning feedback: Design VR or AR scenarios that adjust to individual performance data, providing tailored challenges and feedback that align with each learner's learning curve and needs.
6. To enable a detailed review of learner interactions through XR data visualization: Use XR to generate and display detailed data visualizations of learner interactions and progress within virtual environments, aiding in the deep analysis and interpretation of complex learner data.
7. To facilitate collaborative planning and reflection using XR tools: Integrate collaborative VR spaces where learners and educators can jointly reflect on performance, discuss assessment results, and plan future learning activities in an immersive interactive setting.
8. To utilize XR to maintain continuous communication with learners and parents about educational progress: Develop AR applications that parents and learners can use at home to view updates on academic progress, upcoming learning opportunities, and feedback on assessments in an engaging and accessible way.

Table A15. Competency: Accessibility and inclusion.

1. To employ XR technologies to create immersive and adaptive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of learners, including those with physical, sensory, or cognitive disabilities. For example, using virtual reality to simulate real-world environments that are physically inaccessible to some learners.
2. To design and implement XR-based pedagogical strategies that provide personalized learning experiences. This could involve using augmented reality to overlay digital information on physical objects, enhancing the learning experience for visually or hearing-impaired students.
3. To utilize XR to offer multisensory educational content, making learning materials accessible through visual, auditory, and tactile stimuli. This approach can help accommodate learning preferences and needs, particularly for learners with learning disorders like dyslexia or ADHD.
4. To develop and integrate accessible XR tools that support language translation and sign language, thereby fostering a more inclusive environment for learners with different linguistic backgrounds or those who are deaf or hard-of-hearing.
5. To continuously evaluate and optimize the accessibility of XR learning environments by gathering feedback from users with diverse needs and adjusting the content and interfaces accordingly to ensure they are user-friendly and accessible to all students.

Table A16. Competency: Differentiation and personalization.

1. To utilize XR technologies to create flexible and interactive learning modules that adapt in real time to the learner's progress, needs, and preferences, facilitating personalized learning experiences at varying levels and speeds.
2. To design XR-based simulations and virtual environments that provide individualized learning challenges and tasks tailored to the specific needs of learners, such as those with dyslexia or ADHD, enhancing their engagement and learning outcomes.
3. To implement virtual reality (VR) scenarios that cater to high achievers by offering complex problem-solving environments and advanced topics that stimulate deeper learning and exploration beyond standard curriculum content.
4. To use augmented reality (AR) to superimpose step-by-step guides or additional information directly into the learner's field of view, supporting differentiated learning paths and allowing students to progress at their own pace.
5. To develop personalized learning plans incorporating XR experiences that integrate real-time data analytics to adjust learning activities according to the student's engagement and performance metrics.

Table A17. Competency: Actively engaging learners.

1. To use XR technologies to create dynamic and immersive visualizations that explain complex concepts in intuitive ways, such as through interactive 3D models and simulations that learners can manipulate and explore.
2. To incorporate XR-based interactive elements like virtual labs, role plays, or field trips into the curriculum, providing learners with engaging and hands-on experiences that are otherwise not possible in a traditional classroom setting.
3. To design learning activities that place learners inside virtual environments where they can experiment with and influence their surroundings directly, thereby centralizing their active participation in the learning process.
4. To utilize augmented reality (AR) to overlay digital information onto the physical world, enhancing sensory engagement and allowing learners to interact with both physical and virtual elements simultaneously to deepen understanding of the subject matter.
5. To select and implement XR applications that are specifically tailored to support active learning goals within various disciplines, ensuring that these technologies align with educational objectives and enhance learning outcomes effectively.
6. To continuously assess the impact of XR technologies on student engagement and learning, adjusting the complexity and interactivity of XR experiences based on student feedback and performance data to better meet their learning needs.

Table A18. Competency: Information and media literacy.

1. To employ XR tools to visualize complex datasets and digital content, enhancing the understanding and interpretation of information through immersive experiences.
2. To use augmented reality (AR) to overlay digital information on physical objects and environments, facilitating real-time data interaction and integration in learning scenarios.
3. To develop and apply virtual reality (VR) simulations that allow learners to navigate and interact with three-dimensional virtual environments designed to represent abstract concepts or real-world data.
4. To evaluate and select appropriate XR applications for specific learning outcomes and considering their ability to present information in engaging and pedagogically effective ways.
5. To guide learners in creating their own XR content as a method of demonstrating their understanding of subject matter, encouraging creative expression and deeper engagement with educational content.
6. To incorporate mixed reality (MR) setups that combine real and virtual elements to foster collaborative learning experiences, enhancing learners' ability to synthesize information from multiple sources.

Table A19. Competency: Digital communication and collaboration.

1. To engage in collaborative virtual environments using VR to simulate real-world interactions, facilitating communication skills and teamwork in a fully immersive digital setting.
2. To use AR tools to create interactive presentations and projects that integrate digital information with the physical world, enhancing understanding and engagement among learners.
3. To participate in mixed reality (MR) environments for group projects and discussions, allowing for the real-time collaboration and visualization of data and concepts across different locations.
4. To leverage virtual spaces to conduct cross-cultural exchanges and collaborative projects, fostering global awareness and appreciation of cultural diversity through immersive experiences.
5. To employ XR technologies to simulate public service environments, preparing learners for participation in digital aspects of civic life through role playing and scenario-based learning.
6. To explore and develop digital identities within XR platforms, understanding the implications of presence and representation in virtual communities.
7. To manage digital footprints and protect privacy within XR environments, applying security practices to personal and shared virtual spaces.
8. To adapt communication techniques and content creation for VR and AR platforms, considering the unique user interface and user experience designs of these technologies.
9. To design and participate in immersive simulations that require coordinated efforts and shared decision making, enhancing skills in digital negotiation and collaborative problem solving.
10. To utilize VR and AR for storytelling and cultural expression, enabling learners to create and share experiences that bridge generational gaps and foster cultural empathy.

Table A20. Competency: Digital content creation.

1. To use virtual reality (VR) tools to design and create immersive 3D environments and artifacts, allowing learners to express complex ideas and narratives in multidimensional spaces.
2. To employ augmented reality (AR) for enhancing traditional digital content with interactive layers and elements that can be overlaid on the physical world, enriching the learning experience and providing contextual understanding.
3. To develop mixed reality (MR) content that combines elements of both AR and VR, creating seamless interactions between real-world and virtual objects to solve educational problems or explain phenomena.
4. To utilize XR platforms for storytelling and artistic expression, enabling learners to craft and share powerful narratives or performances within immersive digital settings.
5. To engage in the collaborative creation of digital content within XR environments, fostering teamwork and co-creation skills across various digital formats.
6. To understand and apply digital rights management (DRM) and intellectual property (IP) laws within the context of XR content creation, ensuring the ethical use and sharing of digital materials.
7. To design interactive simulations and experiences that require user interaction to progress, teaching learners how to script and program within XR platforms to achieve specific educational outcomes.
8. To experiment with XR as a tool for prototyping and modeling, allowing learners to visualize, manipulate, and refine complex data or concepts in a virtual space.
9. To leverage XR technology for creating personalized learning experiences that adapt to individual learner needs, demonstrating the potential of technology-enhanced personalized education.
10. To use XR to facilitate the creation of digital portfolios that showcase a learner's skills and projects in a dynamic, interactive format, appealing to broader and more engaged audiences.

Table A21. Competency: Responsible use.

1. To educate learners on the ethical use of XR technologies, emphasizing the importance of maintaining integrity and respect in virtual interactions and environments.
2. To develop guidelines and practices for securing XR devices and the digital content created or accessed through them, and understanding vulnerabilities specific to XR platforms.
3. To implement safety protocols for interacting in immersive environments, including managing physical space to prevent accidents and understanding the psychological impacts of the prolonged use of XR.
4. To instruct on privacy management within XR settings, where personal data might be more immersive and, hence, vulnerable, including the use of avatars and personal identifiers in virtual spaces.
5. To explore the implications of digital footprints within XR platforms, ensuring that learners can manage their digital identities without compromising their real-world privacy.
6. To foster an understanding of the specific health risks associated with the use of XR technology, such as VR-induced motion sickness and the importance of regular breaks to mitigate eye strain and physical discomfort.
7. To prepare learners to respond to and report inappropriate behaviors in XR environments, such as harassment or virtual bullying, ensuring a safe and respectful digital community.
8. To utilize XR to promote social inclusion, using virtual reality to simulate experiences that foster empathy and understanding for diverse populations and conditions.
9. To discuss the environmental impact of developing and using XR technologies, including energy consumption and electronic waste, promoting sustainable practices among learners.
10. To monitor and guide student interactions in XR platforms to safeguard their wellbeing, using analytics tools within XR environments to detect and address potentially harmful situations.

Table A22. Competency: Digital problem solving.

1. To diagnose and troubleshoot issues related to XR hardware and software, enabling learners to maintain and optimize performance in VR, AR, and MR environments.
2. To customize XR interfaces and experiences to meet personal learning needs, enhancing accessibility and user engagement through adjustable settings and controls.
3. To employ XR technologies to simulate and solve complex real-world problems by creating immersive scenarios that require critical thinking and strategic planning.
4. To innovate with XR technologies by designing unique solutions and applications, such as creating virtual labs or simulations that allow for safe testing and experimentation in fields like science and engineering.
5. To assess and enhance one's XR skills continuously, identifying areas for development in understanding and utilizing emerging XR tools and software.
6. To mentor and support peers in navigating and mastering XR platforms, fostering a community of collaborative learning and shared digital proficiency.
7. To engage with the latest advancements in XR technology, staying informed about new tools, trends, and applications that can enhance problem-solving capabilities and educational outcomes.
8. To use XR to visualize data and complex systems in ways that are not possible in traditional digital environments, aiding in the analysis and understanding of intricate information.
9. To apply XR for practical training sessions where learners can practice problem-solving skills in controlled virtual settings that mimic real-life challenges.
10. To explore the use of AI within XR environments to automate certain problem-solving tasks, enhancing the efficiency and capabilities of learners in addressing and resolving issues.

Table A23. Competency: Embodied learning.

1. To design XR-based learning activities that incorporate physical movement and sensory feedback, enabling learners to experience and understand abstract concepts through body movement and interaction within a simulated environment.
2. To utilize VR and AR to create learning scenarios that require learners to engage physically, such as through gestures or manipulations that correspond to learning tasks, thereby enhancing cognitive processing through embodied experiences.
3. To develop mixed reality (MR) environments that merge physical and virtual elements, facilitating a seamless integration of tangible interactions and digital feedback to enrich the learning process and deepen conceptual understanding.
4. To implement AR applications that overlay digital information onto physical objects, making abstract concepts tangible and accessible by linking them directly to the learners' physical environment and actions.
5. To explore the use of virtual labs where students can carry out physical experiments in a controlled virtual space, thereby engaging their motor skills and sensory perceptions to foster a deeper understanding of scientific and mathematical principles.
6. To incorporate tactile interfaces in XR applications, which provide haptic feedback to mimic real-world textures and resistance, enhancing the sensory experience and aiding in the cognitive integration of complex ideas.
7. To create immersive narrative-driven learning experiences in VR, where learners can embody roles that require them to perform tasks, solve problems, and make decisions that are cognitively integrated through physical interaction.

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